

A Retrospective Assessment of the Outcome of Repair and Resection of the Occipital Encephalocele: A Hospital-Based Assessment**Samrendra Kumar Singh**

Associate Professor, Department of Neurosurgery, IGIMS, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 14-4-2023 Revised: 11-05-2023 / Accepted: 06-07-2023

Corresponding author: Dr. Samrendra Kumar Singh

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Aim:** The aim of this study was to find the outcome of repair and resection of the occipital encephalocele.**Material & methods:** A retrospective study of 50 exclusively occipital encephalocele patients was conducted in between the duration of 2 years at the Department of Neurosurgery and Paediatric Surgery, IGIMS, Patna, Bihar, India. The medical records of all operated cases of occipital encephalocele were reviewed, and relevant data such as age, sex, location of encephalocele, the size of the lesion, operative method, seizure, and hydrocephalus along with postoperative complications were recorded for analysis.**Results:** Of 50 patients, 17 were males and 33 females. The average age of the patients at the time of presentation was 2.4 months, ranging (4 days to 1.33 years). Most of the patients 56% belonged to 3 months age followed by 28% in 3-6 months age group. All patients presented with swelling on the head just after birth. A visible mass was situated in either the occipital (supratentorial or infratentorial). Any overlying skin varied from a thick and wrinkled to a thin or shiny covering. 16 patients (32%) presented with enlarged head circumference with associated hydrocephalus and 3 patients (6%) diagnosed with Dandy-Walker cyst. 3 (6%) patients were suspected developmental delay and mental disorders. 30 (15%) patients also had seizure. 8 (16%) patients admitted with the complication of sac rupture with cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) leakage, 2 (4%) patients having rupture of sac after the admission and 2 (4%) patients admitted with the complaint of haemorrhage from the thin and shiny covering skin of the sac. Postoperatively, only 4 (2%) patients had CSF leakage from the repaired wound. 3 (6%) patients developed Hydrocephalus after the repair of protrude sac.**Conclusion:** Encephalocele is commonly seen in the practice of neurosurgery in the world. Modern neuroimaging, neurosurgical techniques, and neonatal neurological intensive care have greatly improved morbidity and mortality in the care of encephalocele.**Keywords:** Cerebrospinal fluid, encephalocele, hydrocephalus, IQ, ventriculoperitoneal shunt.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Encephaloceles are congenital group of disorder in which there is a protrusion of brain with or without the protrusion of the meninges through a defect in the skull. [1,2] The estimated worldwide prevalence is 0.8–4 per 10,000 live births. [3,4] It's an abnormal leakage of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) and herniation of brain tissue and meningeal membranes through a defect in the bony skull. It's a rare congenital condition and occurs approximately in 1 per 5000 live births. [5]

It is one form of neural tube defects as the other two, anencephaly and spinal bifida. [6] Mesodermal abnormality is thought to be an important factor that causes a defect in calvarium and dura through which protrudes the brain tissue. The exact etiology of the disease is complex, and the associated risk factors have remained obscure. Some studies do show an association between

certain risk factors such as hyperthermia, aflatoxin, genetic background, maternal nutritional deficiency, or other environmental factors. [1,4,7,8] Encephaloceles are generally classified based on the anatomical location where 75% of encephaloceles are located in the occipital region, 13–15% are situated in the frontal ethmoidal region, and 10–12% in the parietal or the sphenoidal region. [9]

Children born with large encephalocele sac containing the brain tissue is the single most important risk factor for survival. [4] In our part of the world, there is no prenatal screening of encephalocele during pregnancy; therefore, the prevalence of encephalocele is higher where prenatal screening is routinely done. The women have option to terminate the pregnancy in case severe form of encephalocele is detected. [10]

Morbidity and mortality rate of occipital encephalocele are quite variable, and was high in the past compared to the present day, [11,12] A significant proportion of these children lack normal developmental milestones and may have mental and growth retardation, seizures, ataxia, and visual impairment. [13]

The aim of this study was to assess the neurosurgical management of hydrocephalus associated with occipital encephalocele and to correlate the clinical outcome with the presence of hydrocephalus in these pediatric patients.

Material & Methods

A retrospective study of 50 exclusively occipital encephalocele patients was conducted in between the duration of 2 years at the Department of Neurosurgery and Paediatric Surgery, IGIMS, Patna, Bihar, India The medical records of all operated cases of occipital encephalocele were reviewed, and relevant data such as age, sex, location of encephalocele, the size of the lesion, operative method, seizure, and hydrocephalus along with postoperative complications were recorded for analysis.

Patients with follow-up of 18 months were included in the study. These patients were evaluated by computed tomography scan of the brain, magnetic resonance imaging, and ultrasound where appropriate. Patients with other malformations, large lesions, and a significant amount of cerebral tissue in the sac that could not

be repaired without attendant risks, associated syndrome of microcephaly were excluded from this study. Developmental delays and cognition were assessed by senior residents and operating surgeon that were part of the surgical team using examination and interpretation of follow-up questions to the patient's family rather than more quantitative measures such as hydrocephalus outcome questionnaires. [14] Patients who developed complications and delayed milestones were regarded as no improvement and those who did not develop deficits and achieved appropriate milestones were regarded as improved with follow-up examination. Direct excision and repair of encephalocele were done and herniated part of the brain which was gliosed and nonviable; safely removed. Dural defect closed in a watertight fashion; graft from pericranium used where necessary and fibrin glue was applied to strengthen the graft. Ventriculoperitoneal (VP) shunt was placed when hydrocephalus was present. Sacs that ruptured before admission were managed by covering it with normal saline soaked gauze in sterile fashion and were taken to operation theater to repair as soon as possible. We also described postsurgical complications and 18 months follow-up.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS 14 for windows student version Chicago Illinois, USA software and the relevant descriptive statistic is presented.

Results

Table 1: Demographic data

Age groups	N%
Up to 3 months	28 (56)
3-6 months	14 (28)
6-12 months	5 (10)
1 year and more	3 (6)
Gender	
Male	17 (34)
Female	33 (66)

Of 50 patients, 17 were males and 33 females. The average age of the patients at the time of presentation was 2.4 months, ranging (4 days to 1.33 years). Most of the patients 56% belonged to 3 months age followed by 28% in 3-6 months age group.

Table 2: Occipital Encephalocele and Associated Features

Association	Encephaloceles (%)
Enlarged head circumference with associated hydrocephalus	16 (32)
Dandy-Walker cyst	3 (6)
Seizure	30 (15)
Suspected developmental delay and mental disorder	3 (6)

All patients presented with swelling on the head just after birth. A visible mass was situated in either the occipital (supratentorial or infratentorial). Any overlying skin varied from a thick and wrinkled to a thin or shiny covering. 16 patients (32%) presented with enlarged head circumference with

associated hydrocephalus and 3 patients (6%) diagnosed with Dandy-Walker cyst. 3 (6%) patients were suspected developmental delay and mental disorders. 30 (15%) patients also had seizure.

Table 3: Complications of Occipital Encephalocele

Pre-operative Complications	N (%)
Patients admitted with the complication of sac rupture with CSF leakage from the thin and shiny covering skin of the sac	8 (16)
Patients having rupture of sac after the admission	2 (4)
Patient admitted with the complaint of haemorrhage	2 (4)
Patients with hydrocephalus preoperatively	60 (30)
Patients with seizure	30 (15)
Post-operative Complications	
Patient had CSF leakage from the repair wound	4 (2)
Patients developed hydrocephalus after the repair of protrude sac	3 (6)
Patient did not recover from anesthesia	2 (1)

8 (16%) patients admitted with the complication of sac rupture with cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) leakage, 2 (4%) patients having rupture of sac after the admission and 2 (4%) patients admitted with the complaint of haemorrhage from the thin and shiny covering skin of the sac. Postoperatively, only 4 (2%) patients had CSF leakage from the repaired wound. 3 (6%) patients developed Hydrocephalus after the repair of protrude sac.

Discussion

Encephalomeningocele is a congenital anomaly characterized by protrusion of meninge-sand/or brain tissue from a skull defect. It is one form of neural tube defects as the other two, anencephaly and spinal bifida. [6] The relation between maternal levels of folate and the incidence of encephalocele is unclear, but there is clear evidence about the protective effect of folate in myelomeningocele. [15,16] Meningoencephalocele is diagnosed antenatally using sonography. It can achieve diagnostic accuracy in 80% of cases. [17] Other imaging modalities including: CT scan, MRI, and MRA can also be used for further detailed evaluation but their use has been limited due to the rarity of this anomaly. Several factors influence the prognosis of patients with Meningoencephalocele. The sac size and the amount of herniated brain tissue determines the prognosis. In addition, hydrocephaly, infections, and other anomalies accompanying the condition determine the prognosis as well. The mortality rate approaches 30% despite the applied appropriate treatments. [18]

Of 50 patients, 17 were males and 33 females. The average age of the patients at the time of presentation was 2.4 months, ranging (4 days to 1.33 years). Most of the patients 56% belonged to 3 months age followed by 28% in 3-6 months age group. All patients presented with swelling on the head just after birth. A visible mass was situated in either the occipital (supratocular or infratocular). Any overlying skin varied from a thick and wrinkled to a thin or shiny covering. 16 patients (32%) presented with enlarged head circumference with associated hydrocephalus and 3 patients (6%)

diagnosed with Dandy–Walker cyst. 3 (6%) patients were suspected developmental delay and mental disorders. 30 (15%) patients also had seizure. Bui et al [19] reported that occipital encephalocele is commonly associated with hydrocephalus compared to other types of encephalocele. Gregor J. et al, found that MRI could reveal the exact anatomical description of the meningoencephalocele and displaced brain structures, and showed the typical features of Chiari III malformation in some cases. It also revealed the configuration of the brain stem regions. Moreover, postnatal follow-up MRI confirmed the prenatal findings and showed additional morphological information such as vascular anatomy. [20] Furthermore, Magnetic Resonance Angiography is the optimal investigation to visualize the relationship of the sac to the venous sinuses. While CT scans are used to detect the extent of cranial defect. [21] The operative procedure additionally includes the management of possible loss of copious quantities of CSF causing superimposed electrolyte imbalance. Infants with encephalocele can develop sudden hypothermia due to dysfunction of autonomic control below the present defect. [22] Thus, urgent consideration and management must be given to hypothermia, blood loss, and its associated complications. The surgery is advised to be done as promptly as possible to escape life threatening complications such as central nervous system (CNS) infections, respiratory distress, aspiration pneumonia, irreversible impairment of vagus nerve, and hypothermia. [23]

8 (16%) patients admitted with the complication of sac rupture with cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) leakage, 2 (4%) patients having rupture of sac after the admission and 2 (4%) patients admitted with the complaint of haemorrhage from the thin and shiny covering skin of the sac. Postoperatively, only 4 (2%) patients had CSF leakage from the repaired wound. 3 (6%) patients developed Hydrocephalus after the repair of protrude sac.

Conclusion

Encephalocele is commonly seen in the practice of neurosurgery in the world and in Pakistan. It is associated with other congenital anomalies such as hydrocephalus, Dandy–Walker malformation, and microcephaly. Modern neuroimaging, neurosurgical techniques, and neonatal neurological intensive care have greatly improved morbidity and mortality in the care of encephalocele. It's treatment like excision and repair when done in early age, greatly reduces complications like CSF leak, reduced IQ level of the patients and other effects of associated anomalies are controlled in time. Parents have no difficulty in taking care of their children after repair. Therefore, early repair and excision of occipital encephalocele is recommended.

References

1. Agthong S, Wiwanitkit V. Encephalomeningocele cases over 10 years in Thailand: a case series. *BMC neurology*. 2002 Dec;2(1):1-5.
2. Lo BW, Kulkarni AV, Rutka JT, Jea A, Drake JM, Lamberti-Pasculli M, Dirks PB, Thabane L. Clinical predictors of developmental outcome in patients with cephaloceles. *Journal of Neurosurgery: Pediatrics*. 2008 Oct 1;2(4):254-7.
3. Lo BW, Kulkarni AV, Rutka JT, Jea A, Drake JM, Lamberti-Pasculli M, Dirks PB, Thabane L. Clinical predictors of developmental outcome in patients with cephaloceles. *Journal of Neurosurgery: Pediatrics*. 2008 Oct 1;2(4):254-7.
4. Siffel C, Wong LY, Olney RS, Correa A. Survival of infants diagnosed with encephalocele in Atlanta, 1979–98. *Paediatric and perinatal epidemiology*. 2003 Jan;17(1):40-8.
5. Walia B, Bhargava P, Sandhu K. Giant occipital encephalocele. *Medical Journal Armed Forces India*. 2005 Jul 1;61(3):293-4.
6. Suwanwela C, Sukabote C, Suwanwela N. Frontoethmoidal encephalomeningocele. *Surgery*. 1971 Apr 1;69(4):617-25.
7. Wen S, Ethen M, Langlois PH, Mitchell LE. Prevalence of encephalocele in Texas, 1999–2002. *American Journal of Medical Genetics Part A*. 2007 Sep 15;143(18):2150-5.
8. Sadewa AH, Sutomo R, Istiadjud M, Nishiyama K, Shirakawa T, Matsuo M, Nishio H. C677T mutation in the MTHFR gene was not found in patients with frontoethmoidal encephalocele in East Java, Indonesia. *Pediatrics international*. 2004 Aug;46(4):409-14.
9. Raja RA, Qureshi AA, Memon AR, Ali H, Dev V. Pattern of encephalocoeles: a case series. *J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad*. 2008; 20(1):125-8.
10. Allen WP, Stevenson RE, Thompson SJ, Dean JH. The impact of prenatal diagnosis on NTD surveillance. *Prenatal diagnosis*. 1996 Jun;16(6):531-5.
11. LORBER J. The prognosis of occipital encephalocele. *Developmental Medicine & Child Neurology*. 1967 Feb; 9:75-86.
12. Bui CJ, Tubbs RS, Shannon CN, Acakpo-Satchivi L, Wellons JC, Blount JP, Oakes WJ. Institutional experience with cranial vault encephalocoeles. *Journal of Neurosurgery: Pediatrics*. 2007 Jul 1;107(1):22-5.
13. Mahajan C, Rath GP, Dash HH, Bithal PK. Perioperative management of children with encephalocele: an institutional experience. *Journal of Neurosurgical Anesthesiology*. 2011 Oct 1;23(4):352-6.
14. Kulkarni AV, Rabin D, Drake JM. An instrument to measure the health status in children with hydrocephalus: the Hydrocephalus Outcome Questionnaire. *Journal of Neurosurgery: Pediatrics*. 2004 Nov 1;101(2):134-40.
15. Thu A, Kyu H. Epidemiology of frontoethmoidal encephalomeningocele in Burma. *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health*. 1984 Jun 1;38(2):89-98.
16. Christensen B, Rosenblatt DS. 9 effects of folate deficiency on embryonic development. *Baillière's clinical haematology*. 1995 Sep 1;8(3):617-37.
17. Cameron M, Moran P. Prenatal screening and diagnosis of neural tube defects. *Prenatal Diagnosis: Published in Affiliation with the International Society for Prenatal Diagnosis*. 2009 Apr;29(4):402-11.
18. Kıymaz N, Yılmaz N, Demir İ, Keskin S. Prognostic factors in patients with occipital encephalocele. *Pediatric neurosurgery*. 2010 Jun 1;46(1):6-11.
19. Bui CJ, Tubbs RS, Shannon CN, Acakpo-Satchivi L, Wellons JC, Blount JP, Oakes WJ. Institutional experience with cranial vault encephalocoeles. *Journal of Neurosurgery: Pediatrics*. 2007 Jul 1;107(1):22-5.
20. Kasprian GJ, Paldino MJ, Mehollin-Ray AR, Shetty A, Williams JL, Lee W, Cassady CI. Prenatal imaging of occipital encephalocoeles. *Fetal Diagnosis and Therapy*. 2015 Apr 1;37(3):241-8.
21. Agladioglu K, Ardic FN, Tumkaya F, Bir F. MRI and CT imaging of an intrasphenoidal encephalocele: a case report. *Polish journal of radiology*. 2014; 79:360.
22. Pahuja HD, Deshmukh SR, Lande SA, Palsodkar SR, Bhure AR. Anaesthetic management of neonate with giant occipital meningoencephalocele: Case report. *Egyptian*

Journal of Anaesthesia. 2015 Oct 1;31(4):331-4.
23. Velho V, Naik H, Survashe P, Guthe S, Bhide A, Bhople L, Guha A. Management strategies

of cranial encephaloceles: a neurosurgical challenge. Asian Journal of Neurosurgery. 2019 Sep;14(03):718-24.